

DOI usage : a data producer case

Who are we ?

ILL is a Science facility
The most intense continuous neutron flux
38 world class instruments
2000 invited scientists/year
480 Staff
Location: EPN-Campus, Grenoble (France)

An international scientific collaboration

- Founded in 1971 by France, Germany and United Kingdom.
- Scientific partners that have joined in since then:

Spain, Switzerland, Austria, Denmark, Italy, Czech Republic, Sweden, Hungary, Belgium, Slovakia and India.

Research areas

2011

In practice

Users bring:

- The idea
- Sample(s)

ILL provides:

- Neutron beam
- Instrument
- Sample environment
- Scientific and technical support
- Data archiving
- Data analysis support
- ...
- Travel & accommodation

Scientific Workflow

Improving data archiving

ILL raw data is available online since 1973, immediately after the experiment.

Is it really valuable ?

and access to data.

The project: global picture

Improving data archiving and access

We are not alone 1/2

PANData

Federated data infrastructure for synchrotron and neutron sources.

2007 – First attempt
(4 sources)

2010 – 2011 Pandata-Europe :
networking

2011 -2014 Pandata-ODI :
Implementation

Number of Users shared between facilities																	
	BER II	BESSY II	DESY	DLS	ELETTRA	ESRF	ILL	ISIS	LLB	SINQ	SLS	SOLEIL	FRM-II	ANKA	neutron	photon	all
BER II	2761	284	152	54	39	319	556	302	156	130	29	38	207	15	814	657	2761
BESSY II	284	7068	487	110	298	810	165	94	72	46	263	260	89	57	475	1601	7068
DESY	152	487	3563	88	121	735	194	91	55	44	155	130	103	43	402	1259	3563
DLS	54	110	88	3494	72	739	213	336	35	18	145	149	20	12	448	989	3494
ELETTRA	39	298	121	72	2731	455	85	43	23	4	66	316	9	20	162	906	2731
ESRF	319	810	735	739	455	10728	886	406	235	92	600	1069	144	80	1389	3463	10728
ILL	556	165	194	213	85	886	4338	741	343	229	69	176	349	10	1577	1280	4338
ISIS	302	94	91	336	43	406	741	2755	120	119	43	52	155	5	958	740	2755
LLB	156	72	55	35	23	235	343	120	1348	34	12	131	92	3	455	375	1348
SINQ	130	46	44	18	4	92	229	119	34	726	96	9	97	0	348	221	726
SLS	29	263	155	145	66	600	69	43	12	96	2424	182	18	18	177	974	2424
SOLEIL	38	260	130	149	316	1069	176	52	131	9	182	3656	14	26	309	1524	3656
FRM-II	207	89	103	20	9	144	349	155	92	97	18	14	1087	5	522	281	1087
ANKA	15	57	43	12	20	80	10	5	3	0	18	26	5	452	29	157	452

Source <http://www.pan-data.eu/CountingUsers>

- Harmonise authentication and authorisation
- Standardize data formats and annotation of data
- Allow transparent and secure remote access to data
- Establish sustainable and compatible distributed data catalogues (cross search engine)
- Allow long term preservation of data
- Provide compatible data analysis software
- Promote data policies in laboratories
- The Infra should cover the whole continuum (from proposal to publication)

- We need a clear statement on :
 - Who is the owner
 - If we make them publicly available, how do we protect the Experimental team.
- What was proposed :
 1. The facility shall act as a **custodian** for the data.
 2. **All raw data will be curated** in a well-defined format with a unique ID.
 3. **Metadata** is captured automatically and resides either within the raw data files, and/or in an associated on-line catalogue.
 4. **Access to raw data** and the associated metadata obtained from an experiment **is restricted to the experimental team for a maximum period of 3 years**. Thereafter, it will become publicly accessible.
 5. The embargo period can be extended on requests.
 6. **Analysis of openly accessible data must acknowledge the source of the data and cite its unique identifier** and any publication linked to the same raw data

<http://wiki.pan-data.eu/imagesGHD/0/08/PaN-data-D2-1.pdf>

<http://www.isis.stfc.ac.uk/user-office/data-policy11204.html>

<http://www.ill.eu/users/ill-data-policy/>

The user credentials and attributes are managed centrally.

A prototype implementation (based on Shibboleth) is operational

Many software are developed by individuals.

That's great !

We just want to help to raise up their usability.

- Create / Manage a catalogue of available software (mainly analysis)
- Foster good practice in software development (licenses, code versioning, tests, info about support, documentation, ...)
- The use of Web Services could be integrated into facility portals or ICAT instances

PaNsoft Catalogue - Mozilla Firefox

File Edit View History Bookmarks Title Tools Help

pandata.ill.fr/app_dev.php/

PaNsoft Help & Support Software Catalogue Institutes Search software... Login Register

Photon and Neutron Software Catalogue

PaNsoft is a database of software used mainly for data analysis of neutron and photon experiments. PaNsoft is one element of a larger project, PaNdata, which aims to provide a complete, shared data infrastructure for neutron and photon laboratories.

This database can be freely consulted. It gives an overview of software available for neutron and photon experiments and their use with respect to instruments at experimental facilities.

By **registering** and **logging-in** new software can be entered and it will appear in the database after moderation. Similarly, feedback can be given on the software presented herein and more generally via the forum hosted here.

[Browse software](#)

Software: Recent Software Popular Software

Recent Software

NAMD
NAMD is a parallel molecular dynamics code designed for high-performance simulation of large biomolecular systems.

PORE3D
large software suite for filtering, segmentation and quantitative analysis of 3D images (CT, MRI, CLSM, ...).

Ominc
Logiciel d'acquisition des spectres infrarouge. Ce logiciel permet aussi un de créer des cartographies

IMOD
IMOD is a set of image processing, modeling and display programs used for tomographic reconstruction and for 3D reconstruction of EM serial sections and optical sections.

2.1.0-DEV PHP 5.3.5-1ubuntu7.2 xdebug accel app|dev|debug|4e95977de05fe HomeController::indexAction | pandata_index | 200 111 ms 5376 KB anon. 4 en-US zotero

DOIs for the identification of the raw data sets.

- DOI = 10.5291/ILL-DATA.6-05-579
- <http://doi.ill.fr/10.5291/ILL-DATA.6-05-579>
- Creator = Investigators/PI
- Title = Proposal Title
- Publisher = Institut Max Von Laue – Paul Langevin
- Date = 3rd December 2010
- Data Format = NXS

Deployment phase at ISIS and ILL

In both cases DataCite is the DOI provider chosen.

We are not alone 2/2

CRISP - IT & DM

CRISP Infrastructures

- European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF)
- Facility for Antiproton and Ion Research (FAIR)
- Institut Laue–Langevin (ILL)
- Super Large Hadron Collider (SLHC)
- SPIRAL2
- European Spallation Source (ESS)
- European X-ray Free Electron Laser (XFEL)
- Square Kilometre Array (SKA)
- European Free Electron Lasers (EuroFEL)
- Extreme Light Infrastructure (ELI)
- International Liner Collider (ILC)

WP 17 - Data Continuum - Vision

Aim for better sustainable linkage,
traceability and transparency for the whole
chain of experimental science.

Scientific Idea – experimental data – Publication

Partners: ESRF, DESY, CERN, ILL

Data Continuum

Work is going on

- Test of the APIs (creation/update)
- Review of contracts and general organization.

T7: Cooperate with the major publishers to ensure that publications, issued from data generated at the facilities, provide reference to the experimental data sets.

Future, needs & Conclusion

Work is going on at the facilities

- More professionalism in the data archiving process
- Federation and ease of access to data
- General movement towards open access

The support of organisation like DataCite and OpenAIRE is really helpful.

Policies are necessary but incentives are better.

Need to cooperate with publishers:

- Continue to improve the citation of data.
- Need to enhance the rewarding of data producers. (nowadays lots of metrics exist but none concern data!)
- Need for APIs to track the impact of Data, Using DOIs (?)

Citation on ILL raw data

ILL
NEUTRONS
FOR SCIENCE®
Institut Laue-Langevin

Requested DOI: /10.5291/ILL-DATA.6-05-579

Title: Coherent excitations in phosphate glasses

Authors: A. Fontana, E. Fabiani, G. Baldi, H. Schober, J. Stride

Cycle: 20041

Proposal Number: 6-05-579

Numers: 014150 - 014211

Abstract: We have observed coherent effects in Boson Peak frequency region in vitreous systems ($v\text{-SiO}_2$, $v\text{-GeO}_2$). Our results suggest that in glassy systems acoustic branches already exist even if smeared and less defined. Performing neutron scattering measurements on phosphate glasses using IN8 with two different incident k and IN4 at $k=1.5\text{\AA}^{-1}$ with the hot source, we aim to obtain a double results: to directly probe a linear low- q region of the (q,w) dispersion relationship which is expected to be observed in this system due to the relatively low sound velocity (2500-3200 m/s varying with concentration), and to verify the transverse origin of the excess of modes in the Boson peak frequency region.

Dataset(s): [; Author:Fabianstri; Numers:014150 - 014211](#)

Sample: Formula: $\text{Ag}_1\text{x}(\text{AgPO}_3)(1-\text{x})$
Name: $\text{Ag}_1\text{x}(\text{AgPO}_3)(1-\text{x})$

Parameters:		
Consistance	N/A	glass
Container	N/A	no sample container
Environ Magnetic	T	no
Environ Other	N/A	we need a vacuum box for IN8 and a cryofour for IN4
Environ Pressure	Pa	ambient
Environ Temperature	deg	50K-300K
Exp. Energy	Å	IN8:100meV IN4=36meV
Exp. Moment	Å	IN8=0.3-1.5Å ⁻¹
Exp. Res. Energy	Å	IN8=1;3meVIN4=1.6meV
Exp. Res. Moment	N/A	0.05Å ⁻¹
Mass	N/A	5400
Size	N/A	3600
Specifications (libelle)	X	Other sample conditions

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Questions ?